

OPTIMIZING COGNITIVE LOAD AND DEVELOPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN YOUNG CHILDREN THROUGH MULTIMEDIA LEARNING

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Abstract. *Modern educational systems are increasingly integrating digital technologies and multimedia tools into the learning process. These technologies have a high potential to enrich students' educational experience by making it more interactive and accessible. However, digitalization brings new challenges, including cognitive overload due to the volume and complexity of information presented through multimedia resources, which can have a negative impact on children's ability to learn effectively and, consequently, on their emotional well-being. High cognitive load can cause stress, anxiety and emotional burnout in children. Optimizing cognitive load through multimedia tools will not only improve academic performance, but also contribute to the development of a child's emotional intelligence. Due to the reduction of stress factors, children are better able to manage their emotions in the learning process.*

Keywords: *multimedia learning, cognitive load, interactive lessons, emotional intelligence.*

Cognitive load in multimedia learning. Multimedia learning is the use of different types of media content - text, images, audio, video and animation - to create interactive learning materials aimed at the effectiveness of the educational process, being a way to increase cognitive engagement and assimilation of information, taking into account the principles of cognitive load taking into account the age specifics of schoolchild development and multimedia learning principles. The principle of multimodality in multimedia learning, where information is presented simultaneously visually and verbally complementary, is better assimilated due to the involvement of both channels of information processing. Mutually complementary information helps to avoid fragmentation of information and facilitates the integration of knowledge. Multimedia learning has a significant impact on children's cognitive processes such as attention, perception, memory and thinking. Several cognitive processes such as visual and verbal memory are activated simultaneously. Multimedia materials, designed with cognitive load principles in mind, promote better learning and recall of information, allowing students to use working memory effectively.

Learning materials divided into small logical segments and the exclusion of unrelated and complex animations and background music will avoid overloading working memory, optimizing cognitive load.

Richard E. Mayer has contributed to the research on cognitive load in multimedia learning, in his work he explores how different types of multimedia representations such as text, images and animation affect learning, and principles for creating multimedia educational materials that will reduce cognitive load. He identified key principles such as segmentation,

segmentation of information, coherence, and multimodality aimed at managing cognitive load (Mayer, Moreno, 2003).

Richard E. Mayer suggests that successful learning depends on how well the material is structured. Using combinations of text and images with simultaneous audio commentary reduces "cognitive overload" and improves learning (Mayer, 2002).

Well-organized multimedia learning helps to reduce excessive cognitive load by allowing students to use their working memory effectively to process new information. By using visual and verbal channels, multimedia learning accelerates comprehension and memorization, especially for complex material where verbal explanations are supported by visual examples. Multimedia learning can both increase and decrease cognitive load depending on how the materials are presented and organized.

In multimedia learning environments, the interaction of cognitive and emotional aspects of learning are inextricably linked. Research into the correlation between cognitive load and emotional intelligence will enable the development of comprehensive educational programs that will promote the all-round development of children. Understanding the correlation between cognitive load and emotional intelligence has practical relevance for educators, psychologists and instructional designers, through interdisciplinary research it is possible to develop more effective multimedia learning strategies that will take into account children's individual cognitive and emotional needs. This will make it possible to create educational materials and programs that include elements of interactivity and group interaction, which will contribute to the comprehensive development, readiness for successful adaptation and socialisation of the younger generation.

Methods for regulating cognitive load and developing cognitive skills. Multimedia learning in the early grades is based on principles that ensure effective learning, taking into account children's cognitive and emotional needs. The main principles include:

1. Game-based learning or the principle of cognitive engagement. How the use of games promotes cognitive development and creative thinking. Successful learning requires active involvement of students in the learning process, where activity stimulates the child's interest and attention.

2. The reflective method helps children to become aware of their thoughts, actions and emotions and to develop and stimulate critical thinking.

3. Collaborative learning. The impact of group work on cognitive development.

Using cognitive approach techniques to stimulate emotional intelligence, which in turn affects children's social and learning behavior. Interactive lessons using multimedia technology should introduce tasks to integrate emotional intelligence - orientated elements, through discussing the emotions of characters in multimedia materials or through group tasks that require cooperation and empathy. The use of interactive tools such as educational games or simulations can manage cognitive load while developing emotional intelligence. Interactive tasks often require children to co-operate, empathize and manage their emotions, which contributes to the development of emotional intelligence.

According to the cognitive load theory, John Sweller argued, a learner's cognitive resources are limited and overload can reduce the effectiveness of learning. Therefore, the learning process should be designed to minimize the load on students' working memory. His research shows that cognitive overload leads to poorer academic performance. The structure and

content of instructional material can influence cognitive processes. Research focuses on minimizing unnecessary cognitive load to improve learning. (Sweller J, 1994).

Learning materials should be adapted to the individual characteristics of learners, including their level of preparation, learning speed and emotional state. Adaptive learning systems allow the complexity and amount of information to be adjusted according to each child's cognitive capacity, which helps regulate cognitive load and supports the development of emotional intelligence.

Regular monitoring of students' cognitive load levels and adaptation of learning materials based on the data obtained is necessary. This may include reducing the amount of information, increasing time on task, or introducing additional supports such as visual cues or teacher assistance.

The cognitive resources of children, especially at a younger age, are limited. Also, one of the patterns discovered about the ability to remember and repeat no more than 7 ± 2 elements of short-term memory by G.A. Miller, speaks to the limitations of human memory (Miller, 1956).

Learners may experience overload when the volume or complexity of information exceeds their perceptual and processing capacity. This can lead to reduced learning efficiency, negative emotional reactions, which can lead to psychological problems and somatic disorders. Further, the child may develop negative cognitive patterns or underlying beliefs. Judith S. Beck, in her work on cognitive behavioral therapy, notes that our underlying beliefs, in the form of certain interpretations, are so fundamental and deep that people are not even able to articulate them clearly (Beck, 2011).

Effective multimedia learning involves not only optimizing cognitive load, but also developing students' emotional intelligence. The development of emotional intelligence includes self-awareness: the ability to recognize, manage, understand one's own emotions and the emotions of others, motivation and empathy - is a fundamental aspect in social interaction and influences learning outcomes to a large extent.

Proper organisation of cognitive load and consideration of the emotional state of students can help to reduce stress, anxiety in students, being an important component of the harmonious development of personality, emotional intelligence of the child and involvement in the learning process. Understanding the relationship between cognitive load and the development of emotional intelligence is a key factor not only in the creation of effective educational programs, but also in the ability to harmoniously develop children and their readiness for successful social interaction and learning in the future.

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